

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

AITMATOV AND RELIGION

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Abstract

The article examines the religious and philosophical dimension of Chingiz Aitmatov's work in the context of the transformations of public consciousness in the post-Soviet period. It analyzes the writer's views on religion, his interpretation of Islamic and Christian traditions, as well as the artistic representation of biblical and Koranic motifs in the works "The Scaffold," "And the Day Lasts Longer Than a Century," "The Mark of Cassandra," and "When Mountains Fall." Particular attention is paid to the problem of the relationship between secular humanism and religious ethics, as well as the author's position on issues of religious revival, extremism, and the spiritual crisis of modernity. The methodological basis of the study consists of the principles of historical-literary, comparative-typological, and hermeneutic analysis. The conclusion is made that Aitmatov's religiosity is universalist and humanistic in nature and is oriented toward the integration of universal human values rather than confessional isolation.

Keywords: Chingiz Aitmatov, religion, Islam, Christianity, humanism, mankurtism, spiritual crisis, post-Soviet society, intercultural dialogue.

*"I like studying Islam in Muslim countries and
Christianity in European countries;
I immerse myself in them as one immerses oneself
in culture.*

*Here, I agree with Goethe: 'He who knows only
one
religion knows none at all. Artificial religious
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does not lead a person to the truth, but away
from it.'*

Chingiz Aitmatov

UNESCO data attests to the worldwide recognition of the works of the outstanding writer Chingiz Aitmatov in world literature: on the eve of the 21st century, Aitmatov's books had been published 830 times in 168 countries, with 67.2 million copies in 165 languages. According to the latest UNESCO data, Ch. Aitmatov is named the most widely read writer in the world after W. Shakespeare and L. Tolstoy. His books have been translated into 176 languages and published in a total circulation of 80 million copies. Our famous compatriot is not only an outstanding writer, philosopher, and public figure, but also a man who told the world about the Kyrgyz people and Kyrgyzstan.

And the more time passes without Aitmatov, the more his greatness and the significance of his immortal works, which will continue to educate many generations of young people for a long time to come, become apparent. Reviews of him and his work, regardless of who wrote them, recognize him as a brilliant writer, thinker, and artist of the literary word, embodying the power of human intellect, immortality, and internationalism.

Over the past half-century, a huge number of serious works have been written about Aitmatov's work, his philosophy of life, his social problems, his artistic images, and contradictions. Today, there is a whole scientific field in world literary studies called Aitmatov studies. Today, there is an entire academic field in world literary studies known as Aitmatology. In this context, we are interested in the question of the writer's attitude toward religion, which is not only dynamically reviving in modern conditions, but has also become a noticeable phenomenon in the socio-cultural life of the country, the essence of which lies in an ill-considered leap from one extreme to another. Thus, if during the Soviet era, under totalitarian atheistic pressure, religion was expelled from all spheres of public life, eradicated everywhere, with only a few traditional rituals being tolerated, without which Kyrgyz life was essentially impossible (nike, janaza, sunnot, etc.), in the post-Soviet

period, the ideological void was quickly filled with religious ideology, unfortunately, preferably archaic, pulling society backward. On the one hand, many Muslims gained the opportunity to openly live according to the canons of Islam: to receive religious education, observe all rituals, eat halal food, raise children in the Islamic spirit, perform the hajj to Mecca, etc. In other words, Islam, as the religion of the country's majority population, has taken root in many areas of public and private life. Religious prayers for Kurman and Oroz Ait began to be held in central squares with the participation of top government officials. There were noticeable processes of increasing religious awareness, non-alcoholic events began to be held more and more often, and the appearance of both people and villages and cities changed—numerous domed mosques and religious educational institutions were built with funds from foreign and local sponsors. At the same time, destructive phenomena previously unknown appeared, such as religious extremism, radicalization, the politicization of Islam, the claims of Islamic religious organizations to power, their increased involvement in political processes, and much more, causing concern among society and the state.

Undoubtedly, Aitmatov was not indifferent to the processes taking place and asked himself questions: "... I reflect myself, to the best of my ability, on what religion is. To what extent should we devote ourselves to religion? To what extent can we trust it?" [1] Distressed by this, in one of his interviews he said: "...the crisis of religious consciousness... has already begun. I realized this recently when a man who had converted from Islam to another faith died in a village in Kyrgyzstan, and his relatives, who were carrying him to the cemetery, were blocked by a frenzied, angry crowd of local Muslims. The relatives had to take the deceased hundreds of kilometers away to bury him there. If we cannot give way to each other in front of the cemetery, what can we say about life?"

At the same time, he repeatedly repeats the idea in his numerous interviews that "we must distinguish between the great religion of Islam and the people who profess it." He says: "Religion is great in itself. Its greatness can be seen through the prism of the universal development of humanity. How many countries in this world have been destroyed, turned to ashes, how many civilizations have completely disappeared from the face of the earth. Eras and times have changed in the world, but religion has not been erased from the human heart. This is the great value of religion. In religion, we seek the mysteries of man and the universe; in religion, we seek the great power capable of purifying our spiritual universe."

It is well known that the functions of religion and literature are similar in addressing issues of morality and education, in creating and perfecting human nature. According to the writer, literature should have such value orientations as understanding human nature "...so that the eternally great immortal passions constantly prevail in it: creation, continuation, and preservation of the human race, man's knowledge of himself and his purpose in life. For only in this case, if we manage to

withstand the destructive forces of inhumanity and immorality, preserving and elevating the spirit of humanism - only in this case does man define his name as a thinking being." Therefore, in all of the writer's works, the story of the moral collapse of man is condemned ("My Topolek in a Red Kerchief"), Duishen fights against the inertia of social prejudices ("My First Teacher"), extols the best qualities of the human personality such as decency, honesty, truthfulness, justice, protest against the lies and cruelty of the 'adult' world (in "The White Steamboat"), the weakness of human will, betrayal (in "Ascent to Fuji"), etc.

What are the consequences of the revival of religious life, what fruits will we reap from it, what will we ultimately achieve? Why have negative phenomena such as irresponsibility, corruption, child abuse, neglect of the elderly, deception, and ignorance overwhelmed society? Without a doubt, the writer was concerned with the question of why, despite the dynamic process of Islamization, morality, ethics, and purity of thought are in deep crisis.

What is the reason why religion is failing to fulfill its main social function—spiritual and moral revival? After all, it is in religion that the universal spiritual and moral values, proven by thousands of years of life experience, are concentrated. These and many other questions preoccupied Aitmatov, who was not indifferent to the future of his people. The tragedy of the transformations that took place is vividly reflected in his last work, *When the Mountains Fall*, despite the fact that questions of religion are not raised in it; however, the author is deeply concerned about the changes that have taken place in the spiritual impoverishment of society.

In his novel "The Day Lasts More Than a Hundred Years", the writer showed that a person deprived of higher reason becomes a *mankurts*, who will not even stop at murdering his mother, the woman who gave birth to him. "If before, people who were zombies, *mankurts* deprived of reason, were the heroes of my work, now they have turned into real people. How else can we call those who, in different corners of the world today, carry out terrorist acts against people, often without even sparing themselves?"

The writer's planetary thinking is reflected in the novel "And the Day Lasts Longer Than a Century," in which earthly events intersect with cosmic ones; extra-terrestrial cosmic forces respond to people's evil and good deeds. The quintessence of "The Gallows" is the idea of the contradictory nature of human beings: on the one hand, humans subjugate and exploit nature, and on the other hand, they destroy it with their transformations. This idea is continued in "The Mark of Cassandra," where a scientific experiment to create an artificial human turns into a personal tragedy for the scientist, who realizes the monstrous nature of violence against nature, which can lead to a global catastrophe. The writer attempts to answer questions about the relationship between humans and religion. In the story "The White Cloud of Genghis Khan," while the conqueror is doing earthly deeds, the heavens favor him, but as soon as he begins to do evil, the cloud, which in the religions of many peoples symbolizes purity and the divine, deprives Genghis Khan of its support.

There is a well-known statement by the writer's daughter, Shirin Aitmatova, who, while serving as a member of the Kyrgyz parliament, during a discussion of a bill requiring the president to take an oath (vow) before God, spoke out against it, stating that my father, Aitmatov, was a convinced atheist: "This does not mean that this man was a bad person" [2]

Undoubtedly, as a prominent representative of the Soviet generation, Ch. Aitmatov had a secular worldview. That is why all of Ch. Aitmatov's works—short stories, novellas, novels, essays, articles, and dialogues—raise simple but eternal moral issues. In them, the writer fiercely denounces evil, treachery, baseness, power-hunger, and tyranny, while at the same time extolling in his characters freedom of thought, the irrecconcilable struggle between good and evil, exalting justice and people possessing the highest qualities of human conscience, elevating to divine holiness heroic natures whose heroism lay in the nobility of their deeds and in their purity. His works make the reader experience the meaning of human life and conscience, and think and reflect on what a real person should be like and what their highest purpose is.

As a humanist, the writer endows his contemporaries with such human qualities as "the ability and skill to think at the level of advanced, progressive ideas, to think globally, which is, in essence, genuine internationalism, genuine respect for the uniqueness of cultures, national languages, art, and values developed by all peoples." And, finally, it is the ability to think ahead, discerning today the trends of tomorrow. [3]

At the same time, an analysis of the great writer's works in terms of his attitude toward religion shows that his creative work was based on universal humanistic values, which largely correspond to the values of world religions.

In his work "The Cross," the writer, through his character he asked the question: "Have you ever heard of an elderly person who has experienced considerable suffering in life losing faith in God at the end of their life or interpreting divine concepts in their own way? No, if such a thing happens, it is undoubtedly extremely rare". [4 p.50]

As we get to know the works of this great writer, we see that he was familiar with religious values and mythology and had a thorough understanding of the world's religions and sacred writings. Therefore, in his works, the writer uses ancient myths, biblical motifs, and contemporary philosophy.

The novel "The Scaffold" explores the theme of Jesus Christ, although his name is not mentioned, but there are references to "the Galilean," Pontius Pilate, and Bald Mountain, and an educated reader understands that this is a reference to a well-known episode from the Gospel. Aitmatov's Christ in his novel is a collective image of a moral man, and the apocalypse - the end of the world - "comes from the enmity of people," says the writer through the words of his character Avdiya. Living mentally in several temporal incarnations, Avdiy implores people not to allow Christ to be executed. In the hero's memory, there is a great unity of being: it consists in the fact that "good and evil are

passed down from generation to generation, in the infinity of time and space of the human world."

Regarding the role and place of Islam in society, the writer noted: "Islam, in my opinion, like other religions, should occupy an appropriate place in the lives of believers, but in no case should it serve as a reason for isolation from others and, even more so, should it not give rise to conflicts. Its task is to uphold and preach unshakable truths." [5]

Speaking in Moscow in 2005 at the conference "Islam - Religion of Peace," Chyngyz Torokulovich noted: "A provocative campaign is being waged against Islam in the world today, portraying it as an enemy of world civilization. In light of what is happening in the world, I wonder whether the fight against international terrorism is not a total war against the peaceful coexistence of people? Why is Islam being blamed for international terrorism? This is a cunning provocation against the Muslim religion. But the point today is not even that we must defend Islam with all our might against various attacks, because as a great religion, it does not need this. The problem, in my opinion, lies with Muslims themselves, especially religious leaders, who, despite often having high theological qualifications, are not yet able to convince the whole world that Islam has nothing to do with terrorist. Unfortunately, the latter fiercely exploit the Muslim religion, thereby discrediting it. As a result, the world is overwhelmed by tension, one of the main sources of which is poverty and illiteracy, which prevail across vast areas of the globe. Wars are breaking out, which are, in fact, even more terrible than terrorism. The very essence of human rights is being eroded. Conflict between East and West has become an inevitable reality. These problems must also be addressed. That is why it is more important than ever for both sides, in the West and in the East, to adopt a reasonable approach and understanding of what is happening, which would facilitate cooperation between all healthy forces. It is necessary to change the situation where poverty and prosperity, which divide the East and the West, constantly give rise to new social upheavals. In my opinion, this is what we need to talk about more and more now in order to overcome existing problems without revolutions, riots, and bloodshed. [6]

He believed that it should be understood that the negative attitude towards Islam in today's world, especially on the part of the West, is largely shaped by Muslims themselves: "It is one thing when modern, educated young Europeans who know several languages discuss the divine, the Koran, and Islam. It is quite another when a shepherd, even if he is an honest, kind, and decent person, but whose understanding of the world is extremely limited, does so. In general, we must realize our responsibility to the future, develop ourselves, and be creators. Today, as a result of globalization, everything that was closed, isolated, or excluded is opening up and becoming accessible. At the same time, the West, with its greatest achievements in virtually all areas of life, feels itself to be the dominant force. The Islamic world lags behind, sometimes even trying to isolate itself from global trends. But the path to prosperity lies precisely in overcoming this, frankly, huge gap, in acquiring the ability to enjoy the benefits of

modern civilization. We must join in global development and become participants in world processes ourselves. Without this, it is impossible to regain a leading position in the world. Meanwhile, as we integrate, we must not forget our own identity. After all, this is the art of living."

When reporters asked him questions on this topic, he said that he planned to write a novel using Muslim themes. At the same time, he noted that he would leave the choice up to the reader and would not "... impose any ideas on the reader, and at the same time, not give any reason to desecrate Islam. I also hope that among the new generation of the Islamic world, there will be those who, being passionate about religion, will be able to express the spirit of their time, their experiences, and ideas, basing their creativity on the Koran."

In response to a question from the People's Writer of the Kyrgyz Republic, playwright S. Raev, about how many people in the world today see reading the Bible and the Koran as a way out of spiritual poverty, and how all the great writers, from Goethe, Dostoevsky, Tolstoy, T. Mann, and Bulgakov, having reached the pinnacle of their creative development as writers, turned to the "search for God," how do you feel about this? The writer replied: "Both the Koran and the Bible are aimed at purifying the human soul, at showing it all the existing paths of development. In this sense, true literature is in harmony with the Great Words, bringing their meaning to the world... Religion is great in itself. Its greatness can be seen through the prism of the universal development of humanity."

In our opinion, the writer's attitude toward religion is expressed in the words of his character, the futurologist Bork: "...perhaps the time has come, a historical era when all religions could come together to meet humanity, rather than separately and jostling each other? So that a person at the end of the twentieth century could

declare, unlike previous generations, 'All religions are mine, and I am the bearer of all religions, I am welcome in all temples of all cults, and in all temples I am a welcome pilgrim... I was born to Christians, I was baptized, and I will be buried to verses from the Koran. Today I was Orthodox with the Orthodox, yesterday I was a Muslim among Muslims, in Japan I worshipped Buddha, in Sweden I echoed Luther's theses. I am no stranger to anyone in my faith in God, and I am no stranger to the prayers that people offer to our Creator in all languages and dialects. The Creator, who listens to us all equally, suffers equally from our misdeeds, and opens the universe to us all equally, according to our wisdom and virtue... Religion, as Aitmatov understood it, was not only a system of beliefs, but also a deep layer of human culture, a moral support, and a form of spiritual search. At the same time, the writer was critical of manifestations of fanaticism, the politicization of faith, and its instrumentalization for ideological purposes. Thus, religious issues in Aitmatov's legacy are not reduced to confessional affiliation, but appear as a form of philosophical reflection on the fate of man and humanity in an era of global challenges.

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